

OUTREACH WITHIN REACH: CHALLENGES OF NURSES AS SHARERS OF EXPERTISE IN IMPLEMENTING A COMMUNITY EXTENSION PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

Outreach services play a vital role in improving access to healthcare in underserved and remote areas, contributing to the overall retention of health workers at the national level. Mobilizing urban health professionals to serve in these regions is a strategic response to health disparities. This phenomenological study explored the lived experiences of nurses as sharers of expertise in implementing a community extension program. A total of 11 nurses were purposively selected for their experience in serving far-flung areas under the Surgical Networking Extension Program (SNEP). Four nurses from the SNEP, each with over three years of involvement in both the program and their role as experts, participated in in-depth, one-on-one interviews. Additionally, seven other SNEP members participated in a separate focus group discussion conducted between November 2017 and February 2018. Using Colaizzi's method of data analysis, three key themes emerged: *Taking Up the Role*, *On a Mission*, and *Heritage to Live On*, which reflect the altruism-driven commitment of these nurses in providing advanced healthcare services to underserved regions in Mindanao. This study highlights both the rewards and challenges faced by nurses in these surgical caravans, offering insights into the personal significance of their work and its potential to shape the future of outreach services for marginalized populations in the Philippines.

Keywords: *Social Science, Sharers of Expertise, Community Extension Program, SNEP, Phenomenology, Tagum City*

INTRODUCTION

A government regional hospital in Tagum City has consistently sought innovative ways to enhance healthcare delivery. Its mission has focused on making healthcare services affordable, acceptable, available, and accessible to the general population. In line with this vision, the Surgical Networking Extension Program (SNEP) was established. This program operates on a unique model of "dismantling the hospital and setting it up in remote barangays," providing advanced healthcare services, particularly elective medium and major surgeries, outside the hospital environment. By bringing surgical care to underserved communities, SNEP aims to address a pressing need in the Philippines: the significant gap in healthcare access, especially for surgical services in far-flung areas (DRMC, 2000).

Community extension programs like SNEP are increasingly necessary due to the persistent inaccessibility of hospital services, even for middle-class families who are entitled to healthcare benefits (Casella, 2015; Santos, 2014; The World Bank, 2013; Van Gijssel, 2016). In the Philippines, this issue is particularly severe in remote communities where individuals must travel great distances to reach the nearest hospital, which may still lack the capacity to provide comprehensive healthcare, let alone surgical services (Araullo, 2016; Santos, 2014). This lack of access is compounded by out-of-pocket healthcare costs, which remain a burden even with the support of government healthcare insurance such as PhilHealth (Santos, 2014).

Globally, an estimated 400 million people lack access to essential health services, from pregnancy care to basic sanitation, according to the World Health Organization and World Bank (Casella, 2015). In the Philippines, the inequitable access to healthcare remains a critical concern, with private hospitals significantly outnumbering public ones, particularly at the tertiary level (Araullo, 2016; Santos, 2014). This imbalance, alongside poor health infrastructure and insufficient healthcare staff in rural areas, exacerbates the challenges of healthcare delivery (Asian Development Bank, 2009). For individuals in these communities, particularly those with chronic health conditions, the lack of surgical services can lead to a lifetime of suffering and a fatalistic acceptance of their circumstances (Araullo, 2016).

In response to these challenges, many healthcare institutions, both public and private, have embraced the principles of Primary Health Care (PHC) as outlined in the Alma Ata Declaration of 1978 (Famorca et al., 2013). This has led to the establishment of programs such as SNEP, which bring surgical services to geographically isolated and disadvantaged areas (GIDA) and provide training to local healthcare workers to ensure the continuity and sustainability of care even after the outreach program concludes (Karenology, 2016).

While SNEP has been successful in providing much-needed surgical services, healthcare providers participating in these outreach programs face numerous challenges. These include the need to gain acceptance from local communities, establish rapport, and adapt care to the cultural and health contexts of the population. Nurses, in particular, must

develop culturally competent practices and advocate for appropriate resources, all while sharing their expertise with local healthcare providers (Famorca et al., 2013; Omeri & Malcolm, 2004). These challenges are not unique to the Philippines; similar barriers to healthcare access and surgical services exist globally. For instance, in Uganda, the Association of Surgeons of Uganda (ASOU) initiated a successful surgical camp model in response to inadequate surgical resources in rural areas, which continues to operate today despite limited funding and no monetary compensation for personnel (Galukande et al., 2016).

Given the significant challenges healthcare providers face in these settings, this study aims to explore the lived experiences of SNEP nurses as sharers of expertise. Through this investigation, the study seeks to illuminate the personal and professional challenges they encounter, their feelings about the work they do, and the potential solutions to support them in their advocacy for service to underserved and unserved communities. By understanding their experiences, this research hopes to contribute to the improvement of outreach programs like SNEP and ensure their sustainability in providing essential healthcare services to those who need it most.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this phenomenological study was to explore and uncover the challenges faced by nurses as sharers of expertise in implementing a community extension program. In this context, the term “*sharers of expertise*” refers to healthcare professionals who transfer their specialized knowledge and skills to other healthcare providers or institutions with the goal of promoting health, preventing disease, or caring for the sick. Specifically, the focus of this study is on the nurse members of SNEP, a unique initiative that provides major surgical services in a community-based, out-of-hospital setting. By examining the lived experiences of these nurses, this study aims to reveal the personal and professional challenges they encounter while fulfilling the dual roles of healthcare providers and educators, particularly in underserved, geographically isolated areas. Through this exploration, the study seeks to contribute insights that can improve support systems for nurses involved in similar outreach programs and ensure the sustainability and effectiveness of community-based surgical services.

Research Questions

The study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the experiences of the SNEP health care providers as sharers of expertise in implementing a community extension program to those situated in far-flung areas?
2. How do these experiences mean to them?
3. What insights can participants share with their peers and nursing practice in general?

METHODOLOGY

Study Design

Phenomenology, as a research approach, provides an in-depth, descriptive exploration of individuals' lived experiences, aiming to capture the essential meaning of these experiences as perceived by those who have lived through them (Creswell, 2013). This study employed a phenomenological research design, which was well-suited for exploring the experiences of nurses as sharers of expertise in a community extension program. By using this design, the study sought to extract the participants' experiences, identify common themes, and provide a comprehensive analysis of their meaning. The goal was to ensure that the identified themes accurately reflect the participants' feelings and perceptions, thereby uncovering the deeper significance of their roles as sharers of expertise. This method is particularly effective in generating a rich, nuanced understanding of complex human experiences, allowing researchers to derive insights directly from the voices of those involved.

Setting

The study was conducted at a tertiary-level government hospital with a 600-bed capacity located in Brgy. Apokon, Tagum City, Davao del Norte. As a major healthcare facility, this hospital offers a wide range of services, including Medical, Surgical, OB-Gynecology, Pediatrics, Neuro-Orthopedics, Family Medicine-Palliative Care, Oncology, Hemodialysis, and Public Health Unit services. Among its community-focused initiatives is the surgical networking extension program, which aims to revolutionize healthcare delivery by bringing surgical services directly to underserved and geographically isolated communities. The SNEP serves as a unique model for extending advanced healthcare services, such as medium and major surgeries, beyond the traditional hospital setting, thus making healthcare more accessible to populations with limited access to hospital care. The study was conducted from November 2017 and February 2018.

Participants

This study employed purposive sampling to select participants who met specific inclusion criteria relevant to the research objectives. A total of 11 participants were included: 4 participated in in-depth individual interviews, while 7 took part in a focus group discussion. Data collection continued until data saturation was achieved, ensuring that no new themes or insights emerged. The participants were nurse members of SNEP, each with over 3 years of experience both as committee members and as sharers of expertise. These nurses had also served in various remote and underserved areas as part of the program, making them well-suited to provide valuable insights into the challenges and experiences of sharing expertise in a community-based surgical outreach setting.

Data Collection Procedure

The data collection process for this study followed a systematic series of steps to ensure the credibility and ethical integrity of the research. First, approval was obtained from the Master of Arts in Nursing Program Chair at Davao Doctors College, Inc. before initiating the study. Following this, the guide questions for both the in-depth interviews and focus group discussions were submitted to three research experts for validation, ensuring that the instruments were credible, appropriate, and acceptable for the study's objectives.

Subsequently, approval was sought from the Medical Center Chief of the chosen hospital to conduct the research within the institution. Once institutional approvals were secured, the informed consent of the participants was obtained. Participants were fully informed about the nature, purpose, procedures, and duration of the study. Their rights were clearly explained, including the right to self-determination, the right to ask questions, the right to refuse to provide information, and the right to withdraw from the study at any time without penalty.

Data collection involved both in-depth individual interviews and a focus group discussion, which were conducted in a location chosen by the participants to ensure their comfort and privacy. The interviews were guided by a semi-structured questionnaire to allow flexibility while ensuring that key topics were covered. Reflective dialogue was used during the interviews to validate the participants' responses and ensure that their intended meanings were accurately captured. After each session, the interviews were transcribed verbatim to maintain data accuracy. Participants were also given the opportunity to review the transcripts to confirm the accuracy of the data before analysis.

All raw data, including audio recordings, were securely stored in a password-protected computer in the researcher's office. These recordings will be retained for five years after the publication of the study and will be deleted afterward to ensure participant confidentiality. Once data collection was complete, participants were thanked for their valuable contributions to the research.

Trustworthiness of the Study

To ensure the trustworthiness of this qualitative study, the researcher applied Guba's criteria: credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability (Cope, 2013; Polit & Beck, 2012).

Credibility was established by ensuring that the data collected were honest and truthful reflections of the participants' experiences. Verbalizations were gathered using a validated questionnaire, which was reviewed by research experts to enhance the rigor of data collection. The researcher also developed a deep familiarity with the culture of the SNEP and its committee members, fostering a rapport that facilitated open and genuine exchanges during the interviews. This familiarity further supported the credibility of the findings. Additionally, purposive sampling was employed, and data saturation was achieved through interviews and focus group discussions with 11 participants. To further

strengthen credibility, participants were encouraged to be truthful, and their right to refuse participation or withdraw at any time was emphasized, ensuring that only those genuinely willing to contribute provided data. Finally, credibility was enhanced by comparing the study's findings with existing related literature, ensuring that the results aligned with established research.

Transferability was ensured through thick description, a process of providing detailed and comprehensive accounts of the study's context, participants, and phenomena. This approach allows readers to evaluate the applicability of the findings to other contexts, times, or populations. By offering explicit and in-depth descriptions, the researcher provided a foundation for the study's findings to be assessed and potentially applied in similar settings.

Confirmability, or the degree to which the findings are shaped by the participants' responses rather than researcher bias or personal motivations, was safeguarded by maintaining neutrality throughout the research process. The researcher ensured that data were presented objectively and accurately reflected the participants' perspectives. Participant validation was also employed, where participants reviewed transcripts to confirm the accuracy of their statements, further supporting the neutrality and authenticity of the findings.

Dependability was achieved by ensuring that the research design, tools, and methods were transparent and reproducible. The interview guide and focus group discussion tools were validated by three research experts to ensure consistency in the data collection process. This validation allows for the study to be replicated by other researchers, with the expectation that similar findings would emerge under comparable conditions. Dependability was also supported through a systematic analysis of the data, wherein common themes were established from the converging perspectives of the participants (Creswell, 2013).

Together, these measures ensured the trustworthiness of the study, enabling the findings to be considered credible, transferable, confirmable, and dependable within the field of qualitative research.

Ethical Considerations

Before initiating data collection, approval to conduct the study was obtained from the Master of Arts in Nursing Program Chair at Davao Doctors College, as well as from the Legal Affairs Office and the Office of the Medical Center Chief of the participating healthcare institution. Permission to disclose the name of the participating institution was also requested from the Medical Center Chief to ensure transparency and adherence to institutional policies.

Given that the study aimed to explore the challenges faced by nurses as sharers of expertise in implementing a community extension program, the data collection process could potentially involve sensitive and personal discussions. To protect the participants'

rights and well-being, several ethical measures were implemented. Only individuals who willingly consented to participate after carefully reviewing the research information sheet were included in the study. Informed consent was obtained from each participant, outlining their rights, the nature and purpose of the study, and the potential risks and benefits of participation. Participants were made fully aware of their right to refuse participation, withdraw at any time, or decline to answer any questions without facing any repercussions.

The right to freedom from harm and discomfort was a priority throughout the study. Recognizing that some topics may be deeply personal, the researcher took care to create a respectful and supportive environment during interviews and focus group discussions. Additionally, the right to self-determination was emphasized, ensuring that participants were free from any coercion or undue influence in their decision to participate. This right also included their freedom to ask questions, refuse to provide information, or withdraw from the study at any stage.

The participants' rights to privacy and confidentiality were strictly observed. All recordings and transcriptions of the interviews and discussions were securely stored in a password-protected computer, and only the researcher had access to this data. The data will be kept for five years after the study's publication, after which it will be permanently deleted to further ensure confidentiality. Throughout the study, institutional policies on research conduct were strictly followed, and the researcher maintained a professional relationship with the participants, avoiding any interactions that could compromise the participants' privacy or the integrity of the research.

Ethical considerations in data handling were also thoroughly addressed. The raw data, including audio recordings of participant interviews, were securely stored and access was restricted to the researcher. By adhering to these ethical guidelines, the study ensured the protection of participant rights and the integrity of the research process.

RESULTS

Profile of the Informants

The informants for this study were selected based on their extensive experience and active involvement in the SNEP. A total of 11 participants were included: 4 participated in in-depth interviews, while 7 were involved in a focused group discussion. All informants were purposively selected to ensure that they met the study's inclusion criteria, which required each nurse to have been a member of the SNEP for over three years and to have actively served as a sharer of expertise within the program for the same duration. This experience positioned the participants as key informants who could provide valuable insights into the challenges and experiences of delivering healthcare services in remote and underserved areas.

The informants had diverse backgrounds in nursing, each bringing a range of professional expertise to their roles in SNEP. They had served in various far-flung areas, often in

geographically isolated and disadvantaged communities, where they provided essential surgical services and shared their clinical knowledge with local healthcare providers. Their participation in the program not only involved direct patient care but also the mentoring and training of local healthcare workers, making their contributions multifaceted.

The informants' length of service in the SNEP, combined with their experiences in challenging environments, provided a rich source of data for this study. Their roles as both healthcare providers and sharers of expertise made them uniquely qualified to articulate the complexities of their experiences. This depth of experience was critical to understanding the altruism, dedication, and professional challenges they encountered, as well as the personal fulfillment they derived from their work. By drawing on their extensive knowledge and experience, the study was able to capture the nuanced realities of delivering healthcare in underserved areas through a community extension program.

Figure 1. *Thematic map*

Providing healthcare services to underserved populations, particularly Indigenous communities in remote areas, has long been a challenge for the Philippine healthcare system. While recent years have seen improvements in the health outcomes of Indigenous Filipinos, significant barriers remain, especially in accessing specialized services such as surgery. Outreach programs like SNEP have been established to address these gaps by "dismantling the hospital" and bringing advanced healthcare services, including surgical procedures, to GIDAs in Mindanao.

Through the phenomenological analysis of the interviews, three emergent themes were identified that captured the essence of the participants' experiences: *Taking Up the Role*,

On a Mission, and Heritage to Live On. Each of these themes provides insights into the challenges, motivations, and enduring legacy of the nurses who participate in the program.

Theme 1: Taking Up the Role

The theme *Taking Up the Role* captures the participants' experiences of accepting the responsibility and challenge of bringing surgical healthcare services to remote areas in Mindanao. While participation in the Surgical Networking Extension Program (SNEP) is voluntary, the role demands more than just a willingness to serve—it requires dedication, professionalism, and the ability to operate effectively in less-than-ideal conditions. This theme highlights the unique identity the nurses adopt as "sharers of expertise" and the weight of the responsibilities they carry. The theme is further explored in two cluster themes: *Identity of a Sharer of Expertise* and *Scrubs of Responsibility*.

Cluster Theme 1: Identity of a Sharer of Expertise

Identity of a Sharer of Expertise reflects the pride, commitment, and dedication nurses feel in their role as experts who share their knowledge and skills with underserved communities. For these nurses, being recognized as a "sharer of expertise" is not only a professional designation but a reflection of their deep commitment to serving others. This role extends beyond clinical tasks to encompass leadership, mentorship, and advocacy for marginalized populations.

Participants expressed this sense of identity in the following reflections:

"For me, participating in this program requires dedication, commitment, and passion to serve the clients because it will be more challenging considering that the set-up is outside the hospital." (Participant 1)

"The experience is enjoyable as well as challenging and fulfilling. It feels like a big accomplishment to be part of something as noble as this, knowing you have helped people in need." (Participant 3)

"...our presence brought joy to them because they could be seen by a physician and even avail of free surgery, lifting some of their health burdens." (Participant 4)

These statements highlight how being a sharer of expertise is an honor and a source of pride for the nurses. Their participation in SNEP represents a deeper sense of purpose that transcends their everyday clinical work. They view their involvement as an opportunity to make a meaningful difference in the lives of others, especially those who would not otherwise have access to surgical care.

The nurses' role in SNEP mirrors a broader understanding of the nursing profession, which includes not only clinical care but also community leadership, advocacy, and education. As sharers of expertise, they become change agents, working to improve

health outcomes for underserved populations while simultaneously enriching their own professional and personal lives.

Cluster Theme 2: Scrubs of Responsibility

The *Scrubs of Responsibility* theme describes the substantial responsibilities nurses assume in ensuring the success and safety of the SNEP mission. In these remote settings, they are not only healthcare providers but also coordinators, troubleshooters, and leaders, responsible for overseeing the technical aspects of the program. Despite the informal, non-hospital environment, the nurses are expected to maintain the same high standards of care as they would in a traditional operating room.

Participants detailed their responsibilities:

"For me, I believe nurses who join this activity require skills because there is only you and the surgeon during the procedure. Therefore, it is very important for the nurse to be knowledgeable, skillful, and insightful about how things are done." (Participant 4)

"...aside from attending to the surgeon as scrub nurse, the nurse must also keep an eye on the student functioning as the circulating nurse." (Participant 5)

"...coordinating with the health workers from both the host community and visiting group..." (Participant 8)

"Ensure proper aseptic technique is complied with by the surgical team... and coordinate with support services for patient transport and handover to recovery room nurses." (Participant 1)

The role of a nurse in SNEP extends beyond clinical tasks to include logistical coordination, quality assurance, and leadership. These responsibilities are critical to ensuring that the surgeries and other healthcare services are performed safely and efficiently, despite the challenges posed by the rural, resource-limited environments. The nurses must maintain strict adherence to protocols, monitor the surgical process, ensure that all equipment and materials are properly handled, and supervise less experienced staff or volunteers.

The *Scrubs of Responsibility* theme underscores the weight of accountability these nurses carry, reflecting their professionalism and dedication to maintaining the integrity of the program. Their ability to manage these responsibilities, often in difficult and unfamiliar settings, speaks to their competence and commitment to providing high-quality care.

Theme 2: On a Mission

The theme *On a Mission* captures the participants' experiences as they implement the Surgical Networking Extension Program (SNEP). This theme reflects not only the struggles and challenges they face but also the sense of purpose and fulfillment that comes with their work. These nurses are driven by the mission to bring surgical healthcare

services to underserved, geographically isolated communities. Despite the physical, emotional, and logistical challenges, their unwavering commitment to the program and its advocacy propels them forward. Two cluster themes emerged under this major theme: *Hurdles to Overcome* and *Rising Above the Odds*.

Cluster Theme 1: Hurdles to Overcome

Hurdles to Overcome highlights the various challenges that the SNEP nurses face as they deliver care in remote areas. These include logistical issues such as the lack of clean water, geographical isolation, safety concerns, language barriers, and the need to maintain professional standards, even in makeshift settings.

These hurdles are a testament to the reality that healthcare, especially surgical services, remains out of reach for many in far-flung communities. Participants shared their experiences:

"Before traveling, preparation of materials must be done ahead of time because it would be difficult for the team if the materials for the Caravan are incomplete." (Participant 1)

"I am worried every time I travel because I often feel ill from motion sickness. Also, I am scared of the possibilities of being terrorized by leftist groups inhabiting the far-flung highlands." (Participant 2)

"By the time we arrive at the area, we must immediately work to make the site appropriate for the Caravan...we clean the place and minimize any potential object or circumstance that can impair the integrity of the setup." (Participant 3)

"One real problem is clean water... we often have to fetch water from the nearest well." (Participant 4)

"The first time the residents encounter us, they are a bit shy and unsure. However, when they begin to see how we can help, they really line up to avail the service." (Participant 2)

In addition to these physical challenges, the participants noted the complexities of managing cultural differences and language barriers:

"We encounter language and dialect barriers... it's challenging to provide proper care and services when communication is limited." (Participant 1)

"...coaching and mentoring health workers in the community is difficult because I must coach them from basic to complex procedures." (Participant 8)

Despite these hurdles, the nurses remained steadfast in their commitment to the SNEP mission, embodying the spirit of altruism that drives them to make outreach services possible for underserved populations. Their narratives illustrate their resilience and willingness to adapt in order to overcome the challenges they face.

Cluster Theme 2: Rising Above the Odds

While the participants faced numerous obstacles, they demonstrated an ability to *rise above the odds* and continue their work in SNEP. This cluster theme highlights the participants' resourcefulness and determination to find solutions, often improvising to meet the needs of the communities they serve. Despite limited resources, difficult working conditions, and unfamiliar environments, they took pride in their ability to bring life-changing services to people who would otherwise not have access to them.

Participants reflected on the fulfillment they felt in overcoming these challenges:

"It created a linkage through the referral system. All patients who underwent surgery shall have a follow-up with the team... the community is now aware that such level of care can be brought to them, even without the ideal structure." (Participant 1)

"With the help of a flip chart, the community members understand more about what will be done to them, making it easier for them to trust us." (Participant 4)

"In working, we use a buddy system, meaning the experienced ones mentor the novices, especially when we have new graduates as volunteers." (Participant 6)

"Doing some refreshment courses in nursing feels like going back to school... it's challenging but rewarding." (Participant 2)

These reflections illustrate how the nurses, despite the difficulties, found ways to educate, empower, and provide care to their patients. They also demonstrated a commitment to mentoring and guiding new members of the team, ensuring that the expertise and knowledge gained through SNEP is passed on to future healthcare providers.

The nurses' resilience in rising above the odds not only allowed them to meet the immediate healthcare needs of the communities but also contributed to their own personal and professional growth. Their experiences shaped them into more adaptable and resourceful professionals, capable of handling even the most challenging situations.

The theme *On a Mission*, along with its cluster themes *Hurdles to Overcome* and *Rising Above the Odds*, reflects the depth of the participants' dedication to the SNEP program. Despite numerous challenges, these nurses remain committed to their mission, driven by a sense of purpose to serve those in need. Their ability to rise above the odds showcases their resilience, resourcefulness, and the personal fulfillment they derive from their work, making their contributions to the program and the communities they serve truly invaluable.

Theme 3: Heritage to Live On

The theme *Heritage to Live On* encapsulates the lasting impact of SNEP on both the participating nurses and the communities they serve. As SNEP continues to bring healthcare services directly to the doorsteps of underserved populations in Mindanao, it has become a living legacy of the hospital's commitment to accessible healthcare. This

theme explores how the experiences gained from participating in SNEP shape the professional and personal lives of the nurses involved, as well as how they inspire the next generation of healthcare workers to carry on this legacy of altruism. The theme is further divided into two cluster themes: *Learned Values* and *Influencing the Next Generation*.

Cluster Theme 1: Learned Values

Learned Values reflects the realizations and lessons that nurses gain from their involvement in SNEP. Participating in the program not only enhances their professional skills but also instills deeper values of service, leadership, and empathy. Through their experiences, nurses become more adaptable, compassionate, and dedicated to their roles as healthcare providers, especially in challenging environments.

Participants shared the profound impact SNEP had on their professional outlook:

"You will learn how to anticipate what must be done while working in this project. You will develop the initiative to act, even without being told, and to be quick and responsive in all situations." (Participant 2)

"Every time I hear that there is a scheduled SNEP activity, I feel excited and privileged to take part. Aside from its noble cause, the change of scenery makes it more enjoyable, and the co-volunteers are fun to work with." (Participant 7)

"I've seen the difference between working in a hospital and participating in the Caravan. SNEP allows us to gather, have fun, and unwind after a long day. It brings a happy, satisfying, and fulfilling feeling." (Participant 8)

These reflections highlight how SNEP enriches the nurses' professional lives by fostering a sense of fulfillment and purpose. The program also cultivates growth in decision-making, leadership, and delegation skills, as nurses navigate the challenges of providing care in non-traditional settings.

Participants also expressed how these learned values shaped their approach to nursing:

"The beautiful thing about this surgical networking is that you are exposed to different communities... it develops a sense of maturity and helps you attain a certain level of professional growth. It enhances your decision-making and delegation skills." (Participant 7)

"The experience of joining this outreach program is a realization of providing surgical services to far-flung areas... assisting underserved communities with major surgeries outside of the hospital." (Participant 2)

By participating in SNEP, nurses are reminded of their vital role in healthcare, not only as clinical experts but also as advocates for equity and social justice. The values they learn through the program shape their professional identities and instill a commitment to continue serving underserved populations.

Cluster Theme 2: Influencing the Next Generation

Influencing the Next Generation speaks to the importance of passing on the knowledge, values, and commitment to service that the current generation of SNEP participants has gained. Ensuring that future healthcare providers carry forward the program's mission is crucial for sustaining its legacy and impact. This theme reflects the efforts of the participating nurses to mentor and inspire the next generation of healthcare workers, instilling in them the same values of altruism, leadership, and dedication.

Participants described their role in nurturing the next generation:

"The beautiful thing about this surgical networking is that when volunteers and partner health workers in the barangays are exposed to different communities... they develop maturity and professional growth, and it enhances their skills in decision-making and delegation." (Participant 7)

"We have to strengthen service commitment and orientation among health workers to provide quality patient care." (Participant 1)

These reflections emphasize the importance of mentoring younger healthcare providers, helping them develop the skills and mindset needed to succeed in complex and evolving healthcare environments. The participants understood that passing on their knowledge and fostering a sense of purpose among new generations would ensure that the SNEP legacy continues to thrive.

The growing complexity of healthcare practice, coupled with the looming retirement of experienced nurse leaders, makes developing future leaders more important than ever. By influencing the next generation, these nurses help prepare younger healthcare workers to address pressing challenges such as improving patient outcomes, managing chronic care, and providing compassionate end-of-life care.

"Through mentoring and the buddy system, we guide new volunteers, especially recent graduates, to ensure they adapt quickly and learn the ropes of community work." (Participant 6)

Inspiring the next generation of healthcare providers to maintain, if not exceed, the standards set by SNEP ensures that the program's impact will live on. These nurses play a crucial role in preserving the values and principles of the program, ensuring that future generations will continue to provide surgical and healthcare services to underserved communities.

The theme *Heritage to Live On*, along with its cluster themes *Learned Values* and *Influencing the Next Generation*, demonstrates the enduring legacy of SNEP. It highlights how the program not only provides immediate healthcare services to those in need but also leaves a lasting impact on the nurses who participate. By imparting their learned values to the next generation, these nurses ensure that the mission of SNEP will continue,

fostering a new wave of healthcare providers committed to serving underserved communities with compassion, skill, and dedication.

DISCUSSION

The purpose of this study was to explore the lived experiences of nurses as sharers of expertise in the SNEP. By examining the challenges, motivations, and outcomes of their involvement, this study aimed to uncover the complexities of providing surgical care in underserved, geographically isolated areas of Mindanao. Three major themes emerged from the data analysis: *Taking Up the Role*, *On a Mission*, and *Heritage to Live On*. These themes reveal the nurses' sense of responsibility, resilience in overcoming challenges, and commitment to passing on their legacy of service. This section discusses the significance of these findings, interprets their implications, and relates them to the broader literature on outreach healthcare services.

The findings of this study demonstrate that participating nurses experience a deep sense of commitment and responsibility in their roles as sharers of expertise, which transcends the technical aspects of healthcare provision. The theme *Taking Up the Role* highlighted how the nurses embrace their identity as leaders and service providers in resource-limited settings, while *On a Mission* described the obstacles they face and their perseverance in overcoming them. Lastly, *Heritage to Live On* illustrated the long-term impact of SNEP on both the nurses and the communities they serve, emphasizing the transmission of learned values to the next generation of healthcare workers.

The results of this study align with previous research on the importance of community-based healthcare programs in improving access to care for underserved populations. As noted by Casella (2015) and Santos (2014), many remote communities around the world, including in the Philippines, lack access to essential health services. Programs like SNEP play a crucial role in filling these gaps. The theme *Taking Up the Role* underscores the nurses' sense of duty and identity as leaders who not only provide care but also advocate for improved health outcomes in these communities. This aligns with the assertion of Kulbok et al. (2012) that nurses in community outreach must serve in multifaceted roles as educators, advocates, and change agents.

The theme *On a Mission* revealed the significant challenges faced by the nurses, from logistical issues to personal safety concerns, all of which are consistent with the broader literature on outreach services (Araullo, 2016; Santos, 2014). The participants' ability to rise above these challenges—whether through teamwork, improvisation, or resilience—demonstrates the effectiveness of their coping mechanisms. This resilience is echoed in Gruber's (2014) discussion of the inherent challenges in nursing, which require both personal dedication and professional expertise.

Finally, the theme *Heritage to Live On* highlights the lasting impact of SNEP on both the nurses and the communities they serve. Participants described how their involvement in SNEP fostered professional growth and maturity, as well as a deepened sense of altruism. This is consistent with research by Kulbok et al. (2012), which emphasizes the

role of nurses in promoting health equity and community organizing. The participants' reflections on passing these values on to younger healthcare workers also reflect the growing need to mentor the next generation, ensuring continuity in outreach efforts (Gruber, 2014).

Implications of the Study

The findings of this study have important implications for both theory and practice. The theme *Taking Up the Role* challenges the traditional view of nursing as primarily hospital-based care. It underscores the idea that nursing extends beyond technical skills to include leadership, mentorship, and advocacy, particularly in resource-limited settings. This expands on existing knowledge of nursing roles (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, National Academy of Medicine, Committee on the Future of Nursing 2020–2030, Flaubert, J. L., Le Menestrel, S., & Williams, D. R. (Eds.), 2021) by emphasizing the importance of adaptability and community engagement in achieving health equity.

From a practical perspective, the challenges described in the theme *On a Mission*—such as logistical barriers, safety concerns, and the need for improvisation—highlight the necessity for more structured support systems in community outreach programs. These findings suggest that health systems need to invest in resources, training, and infrastructure to ensure the sustainability of outreach services like SNEP. Moreover, the theme *Heritage to Live On* stresses the importance of mentorship and leadership development in ensuring that the values and skills fostered in SNEP are passed on to the next generation of healthcare providers. This aligns with Gruber's (2014) assertion that developing future nurse leaders is essential in meeting the growing complexities of healthcare.

Limitations of the Study

Despite the valuable insights gained from this study, there are limitations that should be acknowledged. First, the study was limited to a specific group of nurses involved in the SNEP program, which may limit the generalizability of the findings. While the phenomenological approach provides a deep understanding of their experiences, the results may not fully capture the perspectives of nurses involved in other outreach programs or in different regions. Additionally, the reliance on self-reported data may introduce bias, as participants may have emphasized positive aspects of their experiences. Future studies could benefit from a more diverse participant pool, including healthcare workers from other regions or programs, to enhance the generalizability of the findings.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and limitations of this study, several recommendations can be made for future research and practice. First, health systems should prioritize the development of support structures for nurses engaged in outreach services, ensuring they

have the necessary resources, training, and safety measures to succeed in challenging environments. Second, mentorship programs should be established to nurture the next generation of nurses who will continue the legacy of outreach work, ensuring that the values of altruism, leadership, and service remain central to these programs.

Additionally, it is recommended that regular impact assessments of the implementation of the SNEP program be conducted. These assessments will allow stakeholders, including the healthcare system, government agencies, and the communities being served, to understand the significance of continuing the program. By evaluating the long-term outcomes, both in terms of healthcare delivery and the professional development of participating nurses, these assessments will highlight the program's contributions and provide data-driven evidence to secure ongoing support and funding.

Future research could explore the long-term impacts of community outreach programs like SNEP on both healthcare workers and the communities they serve. Longitudinal studies could assess how involvement in such programs influences nurses' career trajectories and personal growth over time. Additionally, research could investigate how other factors, such as community involvement or government support, contribute to the success and sustainability of outreach programs in underserved areas.

Conclusions

In conclusion, this study offers important insights into the lived experiences of nurses participating in the Surgical Networking Extension Program (SNEP), illustrating the profound sense of responsibility, dedication, and growth that these healthcare professionals experience in their roles. The three emergent themes—*Taking Up the Role*, *On a Mission*, and *Heritage to Live On*—reflect the complexity and challenges of providing healthcare in underserved areas, as well as the deep fulfillment and professional development that come from participating in such a noble cause. These findings not only highlight the importance of community-based healthcare programs but also emphasize the need for ongoing support, mentorship, and infrastructure to ensure that these programs continue to thrive and serve those most in need. The legacy of altruism and expertise established by SNEP nurses has the potential to inspire future generations of healthcare providers to continue the mission of improving healthcare access and equity for underserved populations.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study was conducted in strict adherence to the highest ethical standards throughout the research process. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring that they fully understood the study's objectives, procedures, and potential outcomes. Participants were explicitly informed of their rights, including the right to withdraw from the study at any point, without any consequences. This process guaranteed that participation was entirely voluntary and that participants maintained full autonomy over their involvement in the study.

To ensure the protection of participant privacy and confidentiality, all identifiable information was removed from the data. Anonymity was rigorously maintained throughout the research process, ensuring that no information provided by the participants could be traced back to any individual. The well-being of participants was prioritized, and care was taken to minimize any potential discomfort during the interviews. If any distress was observed or reported, immediate steps were taken to address the issue and provide support to the participant.

No conflicts of interest were present in the conduct of this research. The researcher strictly followed ethical guidelines to prevent plagiarism and ensure proper citation of all referenced sources in accordance with academic standards. Objectivity was maintained during the analysis of the data, ensuring that the findings were presented accurately and without bias, reflecting the true experiences of the participants. The results of this study are used exclusively for research purposes, contributing to the understanding of nurses who serve as shares of expertise in conducting a community extension program such as SNEP.

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